

Study of Evaluation of Awareness of Hypertension and Heart Disease in Nursing Staff Working in Dr Balasaheb Vikhe Patil, Loni

Prajakta Jagtap¹, Veena Vijaykumar², Priyanka B Gulve³, Tushar D Bhavar⁴

¹Resident, ²Assistant Professor, ⁴Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, ³Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology; Dr. Balasaheb Vikhe Patil Rural Medical College, Loni

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Priyanka Gulve

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Abstract

Background: Hypertension and heart disease are leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Nursing staff play a vital role in patient education, early detection, and management of these conditions. Assessing their awareness levels is essential to improving healthcare outcomes.

Aims and Objective: Our study aimed to evaluate the awareness of hypertension and heart disease among nursing staff working at Pravara Rural Hospital, Loni, and to identify knowledge gaps and misconceptions.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted among 425 nursing staff members. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire assessing knowledge of risk factors, symptoms, complications, and preventive measures related to hypertension and heart disease. Misconceptions were also identified. Descriptive statistics were used for analysis.

Results: Eighty-five percent of participants knew the normal blood pressure range, but only 78% were aware of hypertension risk factors. Similarly, 80% recognised common heart diseases, while 60% understood preventive measures. Misconceptions included the belief that hypertension is only a concern for the elderly (40%) and that salt restriction alone controls blood pressure (55%).

Conclusion: While nursing staff demonstrated moderate awareness, knowledge gaps and misconceptions exist. Targeted educational programs are necessary to enhance their understanding and improve patient care.

Keywords: Hypertension, Heart Disease, Nursing Awareness.

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Introduction

Hypertension and heart disease are major public health concerns globally, contributing significantly to morbidity and mortality. As frontline healthcare providers, nursing staff play a crucial role in preventing, managing, and educating patients about these conditions. Their awareness and understanding of hypertension and heart disease directly impact patient care, early diagnosis, and effective intervention strategies.[1] Hypertension, often termed the "silent killer," is a primary risk factor for cardiovascular diseases, including coronary artery disease, heart failure, and stroke. Despite its high prevalence, many individuals remain undiagnosed or inadequately treated, leading to severe complications. The role of nurses extends beyond clinical care to include patient counselling, health promotion, and lifestyle modification guidance, making their knowledge and awareness critical for better disease management outcomes.[2,3] Several studies [4,5,6] have highlighted gaps in healthcare professionals' awareness of hypertension and heart disease, emphasising the need for continuous education and

training programs. Assessing the level of awareness among nursing staff can help identify deficiencies and formulate targeted interventions to enhance their knowledge, skills, and attitudes toward cardiovascular disease management.[7] This study aims to evaluate the awareness of hypertension and heart disease among nursing professionals, highlighting areas for improvement to ensure optimal patient care and preventive strategies in healthcare settings.

Methodology

This study was conducted as an observational, cross-sectional analytical study at the Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, Pravara Rural Hospital, Loni. The study aimed to evaluate the awareness of hypertension and heart disease among nursing staff. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional ethics committee, and written informed consent was secured from all participants before their inclusion in the study.

A structured questionnaire was developed to assess the level of awareness regarding hypertension and heart disease. The questionnaire included sections covering knowledge of risk factors, symptoms, complications, and preventive measures. Additionally, questions were designed to identify common misconceptions among the nursing staff. The questionnaire was pretested and validated before administration. Nursing staff working in various units of the department were invited to participate in the study.

Data collection was carried out through direct interviews and self-administered questionnaires. Participants were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, and any doubts were clarified by the investigators. Responses were collected and

recorded anonymously to ensure confidentiality. A structured educational session was conducted after data collection to address knowledge gaps and misconceptions identified in the responses.

The collected data were analysed using statistical software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise awareness levels, while inferential analysis was performed to assess associations between awareness levels and demographic factors such as years of experience and educational background. The effectiveness of the educational session was evaluated by comparing pre- and post-education awareness levels. The findings were then compiled and interpreted to guide recommendations for future training programs.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Nursing Staff

Characteristic	Values
Total Participants	425
Age (Mean \pm SD)	35.4 \pm 5.2 years
Gender Distribution	Male 168, Female: 239
Years of Experience (Mean \pm SD)	7.2 \pm 3.1 years

Table 2: Awareness of Hypertension among Nursing Staff

Question	Percentage (%)
Knowledge of Normal BP Range	85
Awareness of Risk Factors	78
Recognition of Symptoms	72
Understanding of Complications	65

Table 3: Awareness of Heart Disease among Nursing Staff

Question	Percentage (%)
Knowledge of Common Heart Diseases	80
Awareness of Risk Factors	75
Recognition of Symptoms	70
Understanding of Preventive Measures	60

Table 4: Misconceptions Identified among Nursing Staff

Misconception	Percentage (%)
Hypertension is only a concern for the elderly	40
Salt restriction is enough to control BP	55
Heart disease always presents with chest pain	50
Medications alone can cure hypertension	50

Discussion

Hypertension and heart disease are among the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Nursing staff, as frontline healthcare providers, play a crucial role in the prevention, early diagnosis, and management of these conditions.

Their level of awareness significantly influences patient education, treatment compliance, and overall healthcare outcomes. The present study aimed to evaluate the awareness of hypertension and heart disease among nursing staff working at

Pravara Rural Hospital, Loni, and to identify knowledge gaps and misconceptions that could impact patient care.[6]

Demographic Profile of Nursing Staff

The study included 425 nursing staff members with a mean age of 35.4 \pm 5.2 years. The gender distribution revealed a predominance of female nurses (n=239) compared to males (n=168). The mean year of experience among participants was 7.2 \pm 3.1 years. These findings indicate that the study population consisted of experienced healthcare professionals who have had considerable

exposure to hypertension and heart disease cases in their clinical practice. The presence of both male and female nurses ensured a diverse representation in the study, contributing to the generalisability of the results.

Awareness of Hypertension Among Nursing Staff

The findings revealed that 85% of the nursing staff had knowledge of the normal blood pressure range. This is a positive finding, as accurate knowledge of blood pressure parameters is essential for early detection and prompt management of hypertension. However, awareness regarding risk factors for hypertension was slightly lower at 78%. This suggests a need for continuous education on modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors such as obesity, smoking, sedentary lifestyle, stress, family history, and dietary habits. [7]

When assessing recognition of symptoms, 72% of the participants correctly identified the common symptoms of hypertension, including headaches, dizziness, and visual disturbances. However, given that hypertension is often asymptomatic, there is a risk of delayed diagnosis. Additionally, only 65% of the nursing staff had a clear understanding of hypertension-related complications such as stroke, heart failure, kidney disease, and vision impairment. This indicates a gap in knowledge regarding long-term consequences, which may impact the ability to educate patients effectively on the importance of hypertension control.

Awareness of Heart Disease among Nursing Staff

The awareness levels regarding heart disease showed similar trends. Around 80% of nursing staff had knowledge of common heart diseases, including coronary artery disease, myocardial infarction, heart failure, and arrhythmias. Awareness of risk factors was slightly lower at 75%, highlighting a need for further education on lifestyle-related and genetic risk factors contributing to heart disease. [8]

Recognition of symptoms such as chest pain, shortness of breath, palpitations, and fatigue was reported by 70% of the participants. While this is a reasonably high percentage, it also suggests that 30% of the staff may not be fully confident in identifying heart disease symptoms, potentially delaying timely interventions in emergency settings. Furthermore, only 60% of the participants demonstrated a good understanding of preventive measures such as regular exercise, smoking cessation, dietary modifications, stress management, and medication adherence. This finding underscores the importance of structured training programs aimed at improving nurses'

knowledge of cardiovascular disease prevention. [9]

Misconceptions Identified Among Nursing Staff

Despite moderate-to-good awareness levels, certain misconceptions were prevalent among the nursing staff. Approximately 40% of participants believed that hypertension is only a concern for the elderly. This is a common misconception, as hypertension can develop at any age, particularly with increasing obesity rates and unhealthy lifestyle habits in younger populations.

A significant 55% of nursing staff believed that salt restriction alone is sufficient to control blood pressure. While sodium intake plays a crucial role in hypertension management, effective control requires a combination of dietary modifications, exercise, medication, and stress reduction. This misconception could lead to inadequate counselling of patients regarding comprehensive lifestyle modifications. [10]

Additionally, 50% of participants held the belief that heart disease always presents with chest pain. In reality, many cases of heart disease, especially in women and diabetics, may present with atypical symptoms such as nausea, fatigue, back pain, or even silent myocardial infarctions. Such misconceptions can result in missed or delayed diagnoses, emphasising the need for targeted awareness campaigns.

Lastly, 45% of the nursing staff believed that medications alone could cure hypertension. While pharmacological management is crucial, hypertension is a chronic condition that requires long-term lifestyle modifications alongside medication adherence. This highlights the necessity of reinforcing education on holistic hypertension management strategies.

The findings of this study have significant implications for improving healthcare delivery. Nursing staff are directly involved in patient care, and their level of knowledge influences clinical decision-making, patient education, and adherence to treatment regimens. The identified knowledge gaps and misconceptions indicate the need for ongoing training programs to enhance awareness and ensure evidence-based practices. Educational interventions should focus on reinforcing the importance of early detection, lifestyle modifications, and long-term management of hypertension and heart disease. Simulation-based training, workshops, and refresher courses can be effective strategies to improve nurses' confidence and knowledge in cardiovascular disease management. In addition, incorporating hypertension and heart disease awareness programs into nursing curricula can help bridge the knowledge gaps identified in this study.

One of the strengths of this study is its focus on a critical aspect of healthcare – the awareness of hypertension and heart disease among nursing professionals. The study provides valuable insights into the current knowledge levels and identifies areas requiring improvement. Furthermore, the cross-sectional design allowed for the assessment of multiple parameters within a single time frame.

A survey was conducted among the nursing staff of a hospital, comprising approximately 15 questions for each participant. Following the survey, the correct responses were shared with the nurses. In cases where answers were incorrect, detailed explanations and educational guidance were provided to ensure a clear understanding of the correct information. This initiative aimed to enhance the knowledge and competency of the nursing staff, contributing to continuous professional development and improved patient care.

Conclusion

The study highlights that while nursing staff demonstrated moderate-to-good awareness of hypertension and heart disease, gaps in knowledge and several misconceptions were identified. Areas requiring improvement include a deeper understanding of risk factors, complications, and preventive measures. Addressing these gaps through targeted educational programs can enhance nurses' competence in managing hypertension and heart disease, ultimately leading to better patient outcomes. Regular training sessions, integration of cardiovascular education into nursing curricula, and active participation in awareness programs can help improve knowledge retention and application in clinical practice. By strengthening the awareness of nursing professionals, healthcare institutions can ensure better prevention, early detection, and management of cardiovascular diseases, reducing the overall burden of these conditions on healthcare systems.

References

1. Grover A, Venkatesh U, Ghai G, Babu V, Aggarwal S, Singh R, Chinnakali P, Kishore J, Singh MP, Goel S, Durga R, Yashwanth RD, Kishore S. Prevalence and associated factors for awareness of hypertension in India: Findings from national survey-4. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2022 Sep;11(9):5766-5775.
2. Rahman M, Williams G, Al Mamun A. Gender differences in hypertension awareness, antihypertensive use and blood pressure control in Bangladeshi adults: Findings from a national cross-sectional survey. *J Health, Popul Nutr*. 2017; 36:23. doi: 10.1186/s41043-017-0101-5.
3. Karmacharya BM, Koju RP, LoGerfo JP, Chan KCG, Mokdad AH, Shrestha A, et al. Awareness, treatment and control of hypertension in Nepal: Findings from the Dhulikhel Heart Study. *Heart Asia*. 2017; 9:1–8. doi: 10.1136/heartasia-2016-010766.
4. Irazola VE, Gutierrez L, Bloomfield G, Carrillo-Larco RM, Dorairaj P, Gaziano T, et al. Hypertension prevalence, awareness, treatment, and control in selected LMIC communities: Results from the NHLBI/UMH Network of centers of excellence for chronic diseases. *Glob Heart*. 2016; 11:47–59. doi: 10.1016/j.gheart.2015.12.008.
5. Miao JH, Wang HS, Liu N. The evaluation of a nurse-led hypertension management model in an urban community healthcare: A randomized controlled trial. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2020 Jul 2;99(27): e20967.
6. Joffres M, Falaschetti E, Gillespie C, Robitaille C, Loustalot F, Poulter N, et al. Hypertension prevalence, awareness, treatment and control in national surveys from England, the USA and Canada, and correlation with stroke and ischaemic heart disease mortality: A cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*. 2013;3:e003423. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2013-003423.
7. Anchala R, Kannuri NK, Pant H, Khan H, Franco OH, Di Angelantonio E, et al. Hypertension in India: A systematic review and meta-analysis of prevalence, awareness, and control of hypertension. *J Hypertens*. 2014; 32:1170–7.
8. Weber MA, Schiffrin EL, White WB, Mann S, Lindholm LH, Kenerson JG, et al. Clinical practice guidelines for the management of hypertension in the community. *J Clin Hypertens*. 2013; 16:14–26.
9. Mills KT, Bundy JD, Kelly TN, Reed JE, Kearney PM, Reynolds K, et al. Global disparities of hypertension prevalence and control: A systematic analysis of population-based studies from 90 countries. *Circulation*. 2016; 134:441–50.
10. Wang Z, Chen Z, Zhang L, et al. Status of Hypertension in China: results from the China Hypertension Survey, 2012–2015. *Circulation*. 2018; 137:20.